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“THE RISING PREVALENCE OF DEPRESSION AMONG THE YOUTH IN MODERN SOCIETY”

Depression has become one of the world’s greatest problems when it comes to mental health that affects our youths today. As the world continues to be more complex and vague, this results in a huge impact on emotional distress and provides confusion for the youths in modern society. Today, where pressure and perfection are trends, many youths are suffering from depression just to keep up with these trends, and this eventually results in unhealthy living in which their physical and mental health really are on the line.

One of the factors that continues to cause pressure on the youths today is the intensified pressure to meet academic expectations and to keep up with the social standards that our society has. Youths are having a hard time balancing academic responsibilities and future career aspirations while complying with the social expectations that people have for them. The fear of failure among all of these is what causes them to have emotional distress and anxiety. In addition, different social media platforms have been used as an avenue to widespread social comparison that leads to fostering feelings of inadequacy, loneliness, and low self-esteem, which can eventually develop and result in depression. Platforms that are meant to be used for connection now contribute to the youth’s exposure to unrealistic standards of beauty, happiness, and success.

Family environment also plays a significant role in the emotional well-being of the youths. In some cases, lack of emotional support and understanding, parents’ separation, and unresolved conflicts at home contribute to the youths being vulnerable to depression. Additionally, lack of financial stability, neglect, and parents’ guidance to their children may also develop emotional wounds that could hamper the youths’ mental resilience. Furthermore, the world’s fast-paced lifestyle isolates children, leaving them behind without proper family bonds and leisure time together, resulting in neglect and even isolation.

Consequences of depression yield in so many areas, in their academic pursuits and responsibilities, social relationships, and even their physical health. In severe cases, it might lead to suicidal thoughts and activities. This emphasizes the importance of early detection for the youths who are experiencing depression today, especially since this mental health problem is silent yet deadly, and many youths today are truly good actors at pretending that they are okay, while in reality they are not.

In essence, the rising prevalence of depression in our society today requires collective efforts in our homes, schools and institutions, social media, and even in our government promoting mental health awareness, encouraging open discussion and conversation, and integrating awareness in our school and institutions. Parents and teachers must also possess and foster a supportive environment where our youths will be more appreciated, heard, loved, and respected for them to boost their morale and self-esteem. No mental health problem is too big if we will collectively work together for our youths and for our futures.

